

IMPACT OF PATRONAGE MOTIVES ON CONSUMERS' CHOICE OF RETAIL OUTLETS IN ENUGU METROPOLIS, ENUGU STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

This Study Examined The Impact Of Patronage Motives On Consumers Choice Of Retail Outlets. Specific Objectives Are To; Examine Whether To What Extent Customer Service, Store Location, Store Atmosphere, Product Assortments, and Product Quality Individually Impact Consumers' Of Retail Stores. The Major Entity Analyzed Is Actual Retail Outlets Consumers In Metropolis Enugu State, Nigeria. The Total Population Is 3, 267,837. Sample Size Of 356 Was Used In This Study. Multiple Regression Analysis With The Aid Of Spss Version 20 Was Used To Test The Hypotheses. Results Revealed That All The Five Predictors Of Patronage Motives Customer Service, Product Quality, Product Assortment, Store Location, And Store Atmosphere Significant. This Implies That, Customer Service, Product Quality, Product Assortment, Store Location, And Store Atmosphere Significantly Impact On Consumers' Of Retail Outlets. The Study Concludes That Product Quality, Customer Service, Store Location, Store Atmosphere, Product Assortments, And Product Quality, Had A Significant Positive Impact On Customers' Of Retail Outlets In Metropolis In Enugu State, Nigeria. The Study Therefore, Recommends That Retail Outlets Should Focus On Improving Quality Product For Their Consumers. They Should Try To Attract New Consumers And Retain Existing Ones Through Quality Products. Retail Outlets Should Concentrate On Offering Good Background Music, Lighting And Good Atmosphere For Customers. The Study Recommends That Product Assortments Should Be Improved Upon By The Retailers To Stimulate Consumer Patronage Motives. The Study Recommends That Retail Stores Should Be Located In Areas That Are More Convenient To Customers. This Study Has Provided Opportunities For Further Research Into The Impact Of Patronage Motives On Consumers' Choice Of Retail Stores.

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INTRODUCTION

Retailing which involves selling goods and services to consumers for their personal, family household use, a vital part of marketing activities and economic growth. Retailing is one of the most dynamic and rapidly changing sectors in most emerging nations, including Nigeria. Retailing is an important activity in the distribution process. This is because retailing involves selling to final consumers who buy for personal, non-business use. In other words, retailing interfaces with final consumption and the retailer with the final consumer. Interestingly, the worldwide, retail sales have been increasing steadily in recent years. To be more precise, it is estimated that global retail sales are projected to amount to around 28 trillion U.S. dollars by 2020 from approximately 22 trillion U.S. dollars in 2016 (O'Connell, 2019). Retail establishments come in many forms as modern shopping malls, supermarkets, grocery stores, restaurants bookstores.

Unfortunately, Nigeria's retail sector remains relatively underdeveloped as over 80% of shopping is still carried out at the traditional shops such as corner shops, kiosks, local markets and free street vendors (Olutuyi, 2018). Nevertheless, a 2013 report by Mckinsey and company estimates that from 2008 to 2020, there will be a \$40 billion growth opportunity in food and consumer goods in Nigeria (Okereocha, 2018). This presents a fantastic opportunity to grow the nation's gross domestic product (GDP) and realize the Nigerian government's Vision 20:2020 with the overall objective of positioning the country as one of the twenty largest economies in the world by 2020.

This research was prompted by the need to help retailers determine the most important motives that impact consumers' of retail outlets. There are a large number of factors that affect purchases made by the customers. Morschett, Swobode, and Schramm-klein (2005) summarized these factors to include product quality, product assortment, price, speed and quality of service, and the atmosphere of the in-store experience. Solgaard and Hansen (2003) categorized several store elements that were perceived significant for the consumers' evaluation and selection of store attributes, including an assortment of merchandise, quality of products, sales personnel, and store atmosphere. Amits, Pradip, and Artee (2010) also summarized these to include a display of merchandise, variety, price, quality, convenient working hours, and easy payment methods. This study covered the following patronage motives, customer service, store location, store atmosphere, product quality, and product assortment. This research work is based on examining the impact of patronage motives on consumer choice of shopping malls in Enugu metropolis, Enugu State.

Statement of the Problem

The major problem that stimulated this study is that while consumers are increasingly shopping, as has been said previously, it is not clear what influences them to shop in the various retail outlets they patronize. However, the current study attempts to examine the impact of patronage motives on consumers' choice of retail stores to bridge this gap in knowledge. Although some studies exist on consumers' choice of retail outlets in other climes (e.g. Uslu, 2005; Chamhuri & Batt, 2009; Prashar, 2013; Agarwal & Guirat, 2017; Razu & Roy, 2019; Bui, Nguyen & Khuck, 2021), these studies were not replicated in the Nigerian context. In addition, studies on similar subject matter were out in the Nigerian context (e.g Oghojafor & Nwagwu, 2013; Igwe & Chukwu, 2016; Akekue-Alex & Kalu, 2016; Onyeagwara, Agu, & Aja, 2019; Okeke, 2020; Eshiett & Eshiett, 2021) were not carried out in the fast consumer goods sector. However, none of these studies focused on how customer services, store location, store atmosphere, product assortments, product quality impact consumers choice of retail outlets in metropolis in Enugu State, Nigeria. This research attempts to fill these gaps.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the impact of customers' patronage motives on the choice of retail outlets in metropolis in Enugu State. However, the specific objectives are:

- Determine the extent to which customer service impacts on consumers' choice of retail outlets in metropolis.
- Ascertain the extent to which store location impacts consumers' choice of retail outlets in metropolis. .
- Ascertain the extent to which product assortment affects consumers' choice of retail outlets in metropolis.
- Determine the extent to which the store environment impacts consumers' choice of retail outlets in metropolis.
- Examine the extent to which product quality affects consumers' choice of retail outlets in metropolis.

Conceptual Review

Patronage Motives

Motives that force or user toward choosing a particular outlet, retailer, or are referred to as motives. In other words, patronage motives are those that influence where a person purchases a product (John, 2003). Stanton (2005) viewed a motive as a force for which an individual finds satisfaction. In addition, he observed that motive turns into a buying motive when the individual finds gratification through the purchase of the product. Aarker (2000) noted that patronage motive is an incentive that propels an individual to purchase something. Kotler (2009) defined patronage as motives that explain why a consumer purchases a product from one dealer or store rather than another. He explained that patronage motives are exceedingly important to individual businesses, and the retailers have always been concerned about the benefits that they can get when they employ patronage motives to attract a loyalty market segment.

Patronage Motives Proxies

Product Quality

Armstrong (2012) described that "product is anything that can be offered to a market for attention, acquisition, use, or consumption that might satisfy a want or need ", while Aaker (1994) said that "quality of product is the customer's perception of the overall quality or superiority of the product or service, with respect to its intended purpose, relative to alternatives, ". Kotler and Armstrong (2012) assumed that product quality is the characteristic of a product or service that bears on its ability to satisfy stated or implied customer needs".

According to Ehsani and Ehsani, (2015) quality of the product is the customer's perception of the overall quality or excellence of the product or service, in connection with the intended purpose, Chang and Fong *et al* (2016) as a result of performance in turn can be labeled as the level of adjustment and freedom from defects or how reliably the product meets customer requirements.

Store Atmospherics

Akram, *et al* (2016) state that store elements of the physical nature of the retail outlet, elements designed to create a certain appearance for the outlet. The design and look of the outlet are created to attract and delight customers. Several physical factors affect store atmosphere, including color, lighting, music, cleanliness, store and merchandise layout, decor, scent, and temperature. Sezgin and Kucukkoylu (2014) concur with this notion, citing that store atmosphere involves a certain look and ambiance produced by the physical features of a retail store to attract customers. This "service cape" referred to as 'atmospherics', namely the overall atmospheric setting of a retail outlet in which various stimulants is involved. These stimulants may include store decoration, product forms, packaging, colors, lighting, air ventilation, scents, music, and display of products in the store. The appearance, attitude, and demeanor of employees, coupled with how they interact with customers, may also affect atmosphere.

Store Location

Martínez-Ruiz *et al* (2010) suggest that once a location is near to the home transaction costs associated with purchase as transport costs and time spent are likely to be reduced. Craig, Ghost, and McLafferty (1984) used the central place theory to explain how people living far away are attracted to larger stores that centrally located in larger shopping malls offering more collection of goods and services than those stores within their own vicinity offering less goods and services. Choudhary and Sharma (2009) identified that retail stores and their location played a significant role in measuring the operational efficiency of retail stores.

Product Assortment

Product assortment as different types of products that a business makes or a retailer offers for sale (Grimsley, 2016). It is defined as the total number of products available in a store concerning different brands, categories their stock keeping units (SKUs). More product variety is observed in modern stores than in traditional stores (Zameer & Mukherjee, 2011). Product assortments can be defined as the different colors, sizes, forms, and prices of products under specific product lines, available in the store (Kotler, 2010). Akbar (2013) asserted that retail managers should look attentively at product variety as an important part of retail management. Product assortment is a crucial factor in store choice selection. According to Koelemeijer and Oppewal (in Skallerud-Korneliussen & Olse, 2009), product assortment significantly contributes to the explanation of the patronage of other retail outlets. This major retailer attribute is described breadth (number of brands/products and depths number of stock keeping units) of an assortment offered by retailers.

Customer Service

Customer service is the act of taking care of the customer's needs by providing and delivering professional, helpful, high service and assistance before, during, and after the customer's requirements are met (Mckinney, 2015). Customer service refers to the service provided in support of the company's products and promises made (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2003). Today's customer service goes far beyond the traditional telephone support agent. It is available via email, web, text message, and social media. Many companies also provide support, so customers can find their own answers on any time. Customer support is more than just providing answers; it is an important part of the promise your brand makes to its customers (Winer, 2001).

Empirical Review

Hariyadi, Armini and Away (2018) proved the significance of store location and store image effect on purchase decision and customer loyalty of modern retail customers in Samarinda. The results showed that store image, store location both have a significant effect on customer loyalty.

Hassan, Zafar, Mohsin (2015) analyzed factors that are affect consumers' choice of retail store, specifically grocery stores. Convenience, variety, product quality, prices and store loyalty were the main factors identified through the study and literature review as factors affecting consumers of retail stores. a research framework designed to evaluates these factors and how they affect store choice. A survey questionnaire was used for data collection from 150 respondents based on which research analysis was conducted.

Okeke (2020) examined the determinants of customers' choice of retail outlet in southeast, Nigeria. Relevant literatures was reviewed. The study found that Product quality had significant positive influence on customer choice of retail outlet. Ambience had a significant influence on customer choice of retail. Price had significant positive influence on customer choice of retail outlet.

Karumba and Ngigi (2018) assessed the factors that customers in Karatina consider when choosing a particular supermarket to purchase of goods and services. The study established that special discounts, security, cleanliness, product quality, fast customer service significantly influenced to customers' choice. Free goods,

loyalty cards, vouchers, background music, frontage and parking outlet do not significantly affect choice of the supermarkets. The study observes that supermarkets that have high levels of cleanliness, security, variety and quality products, fast customer service and convenient operational schedules attract a large proportion of customers.

Richard, Ndengane, Roger and Misheck, (2021) examined the influence of atmospheric store elements on the factors that influence customers` satisfaction. Although small, positive correlations were found between the independent variables (cleanliness, lighting, music, floor adverts, employee efficient service, and employee appearance) and the dependent variables (positive image of store, pleasant mood, time spent in store, intention to revisit store).

Iloamaeke, Nwaizugbo, and Ogbunankwor, (2022) examined the attributes influencing consumers` choice of retail outlets in the fast consumer goods (FMCG) sector. The results from a convenience sample of 323 respondents indicate that all five proposed hypotheses were significant. Customer service, product quality, product assortment, competitive pricing, and store location significantly influence consumers` choice of retail outlets.

Despite numerous studies on factors influencing customers` choice of retail outlets, there is a dearth of studies that cover the five variables services, store location, store atmosphere, product assortments, and product quality. Therefore, this is a holistic study that assessed the various variables and to get a glimpse of factors influencing customers of retail outlets in Enugu metropolis, Nigeria. This aided in obtaining results and as a result closing the gap. In addition, the gap in literature is even more significant than as more literature was so centered in the Western developed countries. Few studies have been conducted on factors influencing customers` choice of retail outlets.

Theoretical Framework

Stimulus-Organism-Response- Model

Mehrabian and Russell`s environmental psychology model is based on the stimulus – organism – Response (SOR) paradigm. This model has two assumptions. First, people`s (customers) emotions determine what they do and how they do it. Second, customers respond with different sets of emotions to different environments (Tai & Fung, 1997). Mehrabian and Russell`s (1974) Stimulus-organism-response model demonstrates the link between environment and its effect on an individual`s behavior. This implies that a physical environment influences an individual`s internal states, which lead him or her to either approach or avoid an environment (Mehrabian & Russell, 1974). Stimulus–Organism-Response Model has been adopted in the context with several studies supporting the relationship between environment and consumer purchase behavior (Baker, *et al*, 1992; Donovan & Rossiter, 1982).

Scholars also emphasize that retail store designs that shape a retail space create or alter consumers` moods and impact their behavioral response (Markin, Lillis, & Narayana, 1976). Donovan and Rossiter (1982) applied the SOR framework to retail store settings and the link between organism and response valuables. The authors conclude that environmental stimuli have an impact on the emotional states of consumers in such a way that consumers may not be fully aware of the stimuli, but the stimuli can indirectly affect consumers` approach or avoidance behavior. This agrees with a study conducted by Baker *et al*, (1994) emphasized that a retail store can offer a distinctive atmosphere that influences a shopper`s patronage decision. Ghosh (1990) argues that atmosphere influences the overall value provided by retailers and defines the concept of retail atmosphere as the psychological effect or feeling created by a store`s design and its physical surroundings.

The authors further stated that store atmospherics impact the shopper through the sensory channels of sight, sound, scent, and touch. Researchers have studied the effects of five popular atmospheric cues that impact the senses, color and lighting (Bellizzi, Crowley, & Hasty, 1983), social factors (Baker et al, (1992), ambient factors, that is, music and lighting (Baker *et al*, 1992; Kellaris & Kent, 1992; Milliman, 1982, Crowding, Eroglu & Harrel, 1986), point-of-purchase displays (Phillips, 1993; Quekh & CannonBonventre, 1983), store entrances, checkouts, and customer service areas (Newman, Yu, & Oulton, 2002).

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research design adapted in this study is the survey method to enable the researcher ascertain consumers’ patronage motives and how they impact their choice of retail outlets in metropolis. The population of the study comprises retail outlets consumers in metropolis of Enugu State, Nigeria. Thus, the population was 3,267,837 the 2006 population census conducted in Nigeria. The sample size was 356 determined using Taro Yamane because the population is so large and it will be too difficult to manage without bias. Convenience sampling technique was used to fill questionnaire. Convenience sampling the researcher selected respondents who were willing and available to participate in the study. Primary data was collected from consumers to examine patronage motives and choice of retail outlets. Multiple regression analysis used to test the hypotheses formulated in the study. According to Hair *et al.*, (2000), multiple regression analysis is a statistical technique which analyzes the linear relationship between a dependent variable by estimating coefficients for the equation for a straight line. In addition, all analyses were tested using SPSS package Version 20.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀₁: Customer service has no significant influence on consumers’ choice of retail outlets.

H_{a1}: Customer service has significant influence on consumers’ choice of retail outlets

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error in the Estimate
1	.971 ^a	.943	.942	.29249

a. Predictors: (Constant), I like shopping where i will be assisted to pack my loads, I shop where customers are treated fairly, I like buying where i can get parking space

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	536.926	3	178.975	2092.054	.000 ^b
	Residual	32.509	380	.086		
	Total	569.435	383			

a. Dependent Variable: I am less exposed to business

b. Predictors: (Constant), I like shopping where i will be assisted to pack my loads, I shop where customers are treated fairly, I like buying where i can get parking space

From the analysis customer services have a p-value 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This shows that customer service have a significant influence on consumers choice of retail outlets companies in Enugu State. With this we reject null hypothesis one and accept the alternate hypothesis one and conclude that customer service have a significant influence on consumers choice of retail outlets. When the p-value is less than 0.05, it means that the result is significant.

Hypothesis Two

H_{0i}: Store location has no significant influence on consumers' choice of retail outlets.

H_{a1}: Store location has significant influence on consumers' choice of retail outlets

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error in the Estimate
1	.935 ^a	.874	.873	.43386

a. Predictors: (Constant) I rarely consider store convenience, A store's' accessibility makes me patronize it. I never consider nearness of a store when buying.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	497.906	3	165.969	881.713	.000 ^b
	Residual	71.529	380	.188		
	Total	569.435	383			

a. Dependent Variable: I am less exposed to business

b. Predictors: (Constant) I rarely consider store convenience, a store's accessibility makes me patronize it, I never consider of a outlets when buying. From the analysis store location has a p-value 0.782 which have less than 0.05. This shows that store location have a significant influence on consumers' choice of retail outlets in Enugu State. With this evidence, this study reject null hypothesis two and accept alternate hypothesis two and conclude that store location have significant influence on consumers' of retail outlets. When the p-value is less than 0.05, it means that the result is significant.

Hypothesis Three

H_{0i}: Product assortments have no significant influence on consumers' choice of retail outlets.

H_{a1}: Product assortments have significant influence on consumers' choice of retail outlets

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.859 ^a	.738	.736	.56863

a. Predictors (Constant) I rarely consider assortment in relation to patronage, assortment is a no factor to me while buying, I buy because the store carries a wide range of products.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	346.620	3	115.540	357.333	.000 ^b
	Residual	122.869	380	.323		
	Total	469.490	383			

a. Dependent Variable: A security lapse in a store keeps me away

b. Predictors: (Constant) I rarely consider assortment in relation to patronage, Assortment is a no factor to me while buying, I buy because the store carries a wide range of products. From the analysis store location has a p-value 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This shows that store location have a significant influence on consumers' of retail stores in Enugu State. With this evidence, this study reject null hypothesis three and accept alternate hypothesis three and conclude that store location have a significant influence on consumers of retail stores. When the p-value is less than 0.05, it means that the result is significant.

Hypothesis Four

H_{0i}: Store atmosphere have no significant influence on consumers' choice of retail outlets.

H_{a1}: Store atmosphere have significant influence on consumers' choice of retail outlets

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error in the Estimate
1	.962 ^a	.925	.924	.35530

a. Predictors (Constant) There is a sufficient display of in-store information, Display motivates me to look at the products more critically, and Fully air conditioned environment makes me comfortable while shopping.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	590.655	3	196.885	1559.659	.000 ^b
	Residual	47.970	380	.126		
	Total	638.625	383			

a. Dependent Variable: A store frequently patronized grows

b. Predictors: (Constant), There is a sufficient display of in-store information, Display motivates me to look at the products more critically, Fully air conditioned environment makes me comfortable while shopping. From the analysis store location has a p-value 0.714 which is less than 0.05. This shows that store atmosphere have a significant influence on consumers' of retail outlets in Enugu State. With this evidence, this study reject null hypothesis four and accept alternate hypothesis four and conclude that store atmosphere have a significant influence on consumers' of retail outlets. When the p-value is less than 0.05, it means that the result is significant.

Hypothesis Five

H₀₁: Product quality has no significant influence on consumers’ choice of retail outlets.

H_{a1}: Product quality have significant influence on consumers’ choice of retail outlets

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error in the Estimate
1	.956 ^a	.914	.913	.35949

a. Predictors (Constant) I think goods sold in my preferred store should be of standard, In opinion my kind of store should sell clean food products, I patronize a store if i discover it sells quality.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	520.325	3	173.442	1342.047	.000 ^b
	Residual	49.110	380	.129		
	Total	569.435	383			

a. Dependent Variable: I am less exposed to business

Predictors: (Constant) I think goods sold in preferred store should be of standard, In opinion kind of store should sell clean food products, I patronize a store if i discover it sells quality products. From the analysis store location has a p-value 0.000 which is less than 0.05. This shows that product quality have a significant influence on consumers’ of retail stores in Enugu State. With this evidence, this study reject null hypothesis five and accept alternate hypothesis five and conclude that product quality have significant influence on consumers’ of retail stores. When the p-value is less than 0.05, it means that the result is significant.

Summary of Findings

This study examined the impact of patronage motives on consumers’ choice of retail stores in metropolis. The specific objectives of this study were tested and the key findings are summarized as follows: The key findings of this study include the followings

- i. Customer services have no positive impact on consumer choice of retail stores in metropolis.
- ii. Store location has no positive impact on consumer choice of retail stores in metropolis.
- iii. Product assortments have no positive impact on consumer choice of retail stores in metropolis.
- iv. Store atmosphere has no positive impact on consumer choice of retail stores in metropolis.
- v. Product quality has no positive impact on consumer choice of retail stores in metropolis.

Conclusion

The aim of this study was to examine the impact of patronage motives on consumers’ of retail stores in metropolis, Enugu State. This study concludes that the consumers’ store choice behavior is significantly impacted by the location of the store, customer services, store atmosphere, product quality, and product assortments. As a result, the study concludes that retailers may need to re-strategize in line with the findings of this study to delight customers and reap the concomitant benefits of profitability, growth, success and alluring retailer image.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following are recommended

- i. The study therefore, recommended that retail outlets should focus on improving quality product to their consumers. They try to attract new consumers and retain the existing ones through quality product.
- ii. Retail outlets should concentrate on offering good background music, lighting and good atmosphere for customers.

- iii. The study recommends that product assortments should be improved upon by retailers in order to stimulate consumer patronage motives.
- iv. The study recommends that retail stores be located in areas that are more convenient to customers.

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